

Alcoholysis Reactions of Stannic Tertiary Butoxide

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Reactions of $\text{Sn}(\text{O}i\text{Bu})_4$ with methanol and ethanol have revealed a greater reactivity of the former. These reactions have yielded mixed alkoxides $(\text{O}i\text{Bu})_3\text{Sn}(\text{OR})$, $(\text{O}i\text{Bu})_2\text{Sn}(\text{OR})_2$, and $(\text{O}i\text{Bu})\text{Sn}(\text{OR})_3$ ($\text{R}=\text{Me}$ or Et). All these mixed alkoxides undergo disproportionation on heating under reduced pressure, the most stable ones being the tri-alkoxy-mono-*t*-butoxy compounds. Stannic *t*-butoxide, used in these reactions, has been synthesised by a new method involving treatment of the tetra-ethoxide with *t*-butyl acetate.

Several mixed ortho-esters of various elements¹⁻³ like Al, Ti, Zr, V, and Ta have been recently reported from these laboratories. In the case of zirconium, the synthesis of zirconium *t*-butoxide methoxides and ethoxides has been recently effected³ by the reaction of zirconium tetra-*t*-butoxide with the corresponding primary alcohol. The exothermic nature of these reactions was ascribed to the formation of polymerised mixed alkoxides from the monomeric *t*-butoxide. In view of the monomeric nature of the tin tetra-*t*-butoxide also, it was considered worthwhile to investigate its reactions with primary alcohols. Several mixed tertiary butoxides of Sn(IV) with the general formula $\text{Sn}(\text{O}i\text{Bu})_{4-x}(\text{OR})_x$ ($\text{R}=\text{Me}$ or Et ; $x=1, 2$, and 3) have been synthesised by the treatment of Sn(IV) *t*-butoxide with lower alcohols in stoichiometric ratios with a noticeable evolution of heat:

(where $\text{R}=\text{Me}$ or Et ; $x=1, 2$ and 3).

The above reactions were carried out in benzene; the reaction mixtures were kept overnight at the room temperature and after removing the volatile reaction products and the solvent, the mixed alkoxides $\text{Sn}(\text{O}i\text{Bu})_{4-x}(\text{OR})_x$ were obtained in quantitative yields.

The mixed methoxy and ethoxy *t*-butoxy derivatives are either white solids or colorless viscous liquids and all of them have a tendency to acquire a yellow tinge on keeping for a few days. The derivatives of the types $(\text{O}i\text{Bu})_3\text{Sn}(\text{OR})$ and $(\text{O}i\text{Bu})_2\text{Sn}(\text{OR})_2$ are soluble in benzene and undergo a simple disproportionation reaction, as represented by the following equation, when heated under reduced pressure:

1. Mehrotra, *this Journal*, 1953, **30**, 585; 1954, **31**, 85.
2. Verma and Mehrotra, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 2968.
3. Mehrotra, *this Journal*, 1954, **31**, 904.
4. R. K. Mittal, Ph. D. Thesis, Rajasthan University, 1963.
5. Kapoor and Mehrotra, *private communication*.

The trimethoxy tin derivative is sparingly soluble in benzene and is stable up to 150°/0.6mm, but decomposes at a higher temperature to give rise to a product in which Sn:OMe ratio increases. Presumably this may be due to the formation of the tetramethoxide of tin, which is insoluble in benzene and is stable at higher temperatures.

The method described in the literature⁶ for the preparation of *t*-butoxide of tin requires a very long time, involving four steps, with poor yields. The well-known trans-esterification reaction⁷, which has proved to be of greater practical utility in the preparation of *t*-butoxides of zirconium and hafnium, has been found to be more convenient in the case of tin also. The ethoxide ammoniate derivative (containing a small amount, ~ 2% chlorine), prepared by the ammonia method⁶, was treated with *t*-butyl acetate and the more volatile ester (CH₃COOC₂H₅) was fractionated. The product, obtained as a dark brown viscous liquid, on distillation furnished stannic *t*-butoxide. Similar reactions of butyl, amyl, and phenyl acetates with stannic isopropoxide isopropanolate are under progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatus with interchangeable joints was used and special precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Fractionations were carried out as described in an earlier communication⁸.

Benzene was dried and purified by the method described earlier⁸. Stannic chloride was prepared and purified in the same way as described recently⁸. Methanol (E. Merck) and ethanol were purified for use by the appropriate Grignard's reagents and fractionation. *t*-Butyl acetate was prepared by the action of acetic anhydride on *t*-butanol. After purification and drying over anhydrous potassium carbonate, it was fractionated (96-98°) twice before use.

Stannic *t*-butoxide was prepared by treatment of the ethoxide, obtained by passing dry ammonia through a mixture of stannic chloride and ethanol, with *t*-butyl acetate and was distilled twice. Ammonia gas was dehydrated by passing through a battery of the benzene solution of aluminium isopropoxide and finally through towers packed with aluminium isopropoxide. Analytical methods were the same as described in a previous communication⁸. Methoxyl and ethoxyl contents were determined as described previously⁸.

Stannic t-Butoxide.—A slow current of ammonia was passed into a mixture of the stannic chloride (850 g.), ethanol (1080 g.), and benzene (150 ml). Benzene (350 ml) was added at certain intervals. Ammonia was passed till the reaction completed. Ammonium chloride was filtered and after removing the excess of ammonia, ethanol, and benzene, a white crystalline solid (92.0 g.) was obtained after drying under reduced pressure. (Found: Sn, 40.50; Cl, 1.80; OEt, 56.20. Calc. for Sn(OEt)₄: Sn, 39.71; OEt, 60.29%.) The chloride ethoxide ammoniate⁶, thus obtained, was refluxed in *t*-butyl acetate (140 g.) under the

6. Bradley *et al.*, *J. Chem., Soc.*, 1957, 4775.

7. Mehrotra, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2266.

8. Gupta and Mehrotra, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 911.

9. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans Green & Co., London, 1956, p. 384.

column at a bath of 140-50°. Ethyl acetate formed was fractionated till the temperature rose to 86°. The remaining *t*-butylacetate was then distilled at a higher reflux ratio (1:40) to push the reaction to completion. Finally the product, a dark brown viscous liquid, on distillation furnished a colorless distillate (75.8 g., 62%; b.p. 106°/5.0 mm) which solidified on releasing the vacuum. [Found: Sn, 28.80. Calc. for Sn(OBu^t)₄: Sn, 28.86%].

Reactions of Sn(OBu^t)₄ with Methanol

(i). *In 1:1 ratio.*—To stannic *t*-butoxide (1.77 g.) in benzene (2.8 g.) was added methanol (0.14 g.), causing a slight exothermic reaction. It was left overnight when a white solid (1.52 g.) was obtained after drying under reduced pressure (30°/30 mm) for about 2 hr. [Found: Sn, 32.0; OMe, 8.8. Sn(OMe)(OBu^t)₃ requires Sn, 32.16; OMe, 8.40%]. The product (1.38 g.), when heated under reduced pressure, provided a colorless distillate (1.05 g.) at 58-59°/0.2 mm. [Found: Sn, 29.10. Calc. for Sn(OBu^t)₄: Sn, 28.86%]. The second fraction (0.03 g.) appeared to sublime (0.5 mm/220°). [Found: Sn, 51.0. Calc. for Sn(OMe)₄: Sn, 48.87%].

(ii). *In 1:2 ratio.*—Methanol (0.23 g.) was introduced dropwise in a benzene solution of stannic *t*-butoxide (1.47 g.), exhibiting exothermic reaction. After about 24 hr., it was freed of solvents under reduced pressure (0.1 mm/32°) when it provided a pasty white solid (1.15 g.). [Found: Sn, 37.03; OMe, 21.80. Sn(OMe)₂(OBu^t)₂ requires Sn, 36.29; OMe, 18.98%]. In an attempt to distill the compound (1.0 g.), a colorless distillate (0.5 g.) was collected (60°/0.3 mm), which corresponded in analysis to stannic *t*-butoxide. On increasing the bath temperature, a white sublimate (0.08 g.) was obtained (0.5 mm/230°). [Found: Sn, 48.50; OMe, 47.0. Calc. for Sn(OMe)₄: Sn, 48.87; OMe, 51.13%].

(iii). *In 1:3 ratio.*—Stannic *t*-butoxide (4.26 g.) in benzene (6.2 g.) was allowed to react with methanol (0.99 g.). An exothermic reaction caused immediate separation of a white solid. It was kept overnight and dried under vacuum (0.1 mm/29°) to obtain a white solid (2.94 g.). [Found: Sn, 41.93; OMe, 34.30. Sn(OBu^t)(OMe)₃ requires Sn, 41.66; OMe, 32.67%]. Action of heat on the product (1.39 g.) under reduced pressure (0.6 mm/150°) showed no change in physical appearance, except some loss in total weight (1.24 g.). (Found: Sn, 44.37; OMe, 42.20%; ratio, 1:3.61). Further heating (0.6 mm/220°) provided a product, which analysed as: Sn, 44.90%; OMe, 44.52%; ratio, 1:3.79.

(iv). *In 1:4 ratio.*—Addition of methanol (0.99 g.) to stannic *t*-butoxide (3.33 g.) in benzene (4.9 g.) caused separation of a white solid. After keeping overnight, filtration, and drying in vacuum (0.05 mm/38°) for 1 hr., the insoluble tetramethoxide (1.94 g.) was obtained. [Found: Sn, 51.20; OMe, 49.6. Calc. for Sn(OMe)₄: Sn, 48.87; OMe, 51.12%]. It appeared to undergo decomposition at a higher temperature (0.5 mm/250°). The reaction in higher molar ratio (1:10) yielded stannic methoxide.

Reactions of Sn(OBu^t)₄ with Ethanol

(i). *In 1:1 ratio.*—Ethanol (0.37 g.) was treated with *t*-butoxide (3.37 g.) in benzene (4.0 g.). Details were the same as described earlier in reaction (i). It furnished a pale white

pasty solid (3.1g), which changed to needle-like crystals after keeping several weeks. [Found: Sn, 31.00; OEt, 11.89. Sn (OBut)₃ (OEt) requires Sn, 30.98; OEt, 11.76%]. On being heated under reduced pressure, the above product (1.6 g.) provided a colorless distillate (1.02 g.) at 95°/2.5mm, which on analysis was found to be the tetra-*t*-butoxide of tin.

(ii). *In 1 : 2 ratio*.—To freshly distilled *t*-butoxide (2.72 g.) in benzene (4.5 g.) was added ethanol (0.59 g.). The reaction mixture became noticeably hot. It was shaken and kept overnight. A viscous liquid (2.33 g.) was obtained, which solidified in ice, after drying in vacuum (0.2mm/35°). [Found: Sn, 33.33; OEt, 25.10. Sn(OEt)₂(OBut)₂ requires Sn, 33.43; OEt, 25.38%]. It changed to needle-like crystals after about 2 months. A colorless distillate (0.4g.), corresponding in analysis to *t*-butoxide of tin, was collected at 101°/3.7mm, when this (0.93 g.) was heated in vacuum.

(iii). *In 1 : 3 ratio*.—Ethanol (1.34 g.) was fractionated into freshly distilled *t*-butoxide (4.0 g.) in benzene (5.8 g.). It led to the separation of a white gelatinous solid. After keeping it about 20 hr. and drying under reduced pressure (0.1mm/37°), a white gel (3.05 g.) was obtained. [Found: Sn, 35.98; OEt, 41.40. Sn(OEt)₃(OBut) requires Sn, 36.19; OEt, 41.34%]. In an attempt to distill it, a light yellow liquid refluxed, but it decomposed immediately providing a benzene-insoluble black solid. (Found: Sn, 63.20; OEt, 36.29%).

(iv). *In 1 : 4 ratio*.—In a benzene (6.8g.) solution of stannic *t*-butoxide (3.93 g.) was distilled ethanol (1.74 g.). General appearance was as in 1:3-reaction. A light brown pasty solid (2.99 g.) was obtained after drying under reduced pressure (0.25mm/37°) for about 4 hr. [Found: Sn, 37.09; OEt, 50.5. Calc. for Sn(OEt)_{3.5}(OBut)_{0.5}: Sn, 37.92; OEt, 50.39%].

Interaction of 10 moles of ethanol and *t*-butoxide provided a solid, which on analysis was found to be tetraethoxide of tin.

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